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**AGE- AND GENDER-SPECIFIC MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN
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 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17554251>**ABSTRACT**

This article analyzes the age- and gender-specific morphological changes in craniometric parameters of the head and cranial index in children of primary school age. Craniometric parameters vary significantly depending on age and gender. Taking these changes into account in medical practice is of great importance in the fields of surgery, pediatrics, forensic medicine, and orthodontics. The development of craniometric studies and their integration with new technologies will allow us to further expand scientific achievements in this area.

Keywords: craniometric indicators, cranial index, morphological changes.

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t.f.n., dotsent

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**KICHIK MAKTAB YOSHIDAGI BOLALARDA BOSHNING KRANIOMETRIK
KO'RSATKICHLARI VA KRANIAL INDEKSNING YOSHGA VA JINSGA XOS
MORFOLOGIK O'ZGARISHLARI****ANNOTASTIYA**

Ushbu maqolada kichik maktab yoshidagi bolalarda boshning kraniometrik ko'rsatkichlari va kraniometrik indeksning yoshga va jinsga xos morfologik o'zgarishlarini tahlil qilingan. Kraniometrik ko'rsatkichlar yosh va jinsga qarab sezilarli darajada o'zgaradi. Ushbu o'zgarishlarni tibbiy amaliyotda hisobga olish jarrohlik, pediatriya, sud-tibbiyot ekspertizasi va ortodontiya sohalarida muhim ahamiyatga ega. Kraniometrik tadqiqotlarning rivojlanishi va yangi texnologiyalar bilan uyg'unlashuvi bu boradagi ilmiy yutuqlarni yanada kengaytirishga imkon beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: kraniometrik ko'rsatkichlar, kraniometrik indeks, morfologik o'zgarishlar.

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ВОЗРАСТНЫЕ И ПОЛОВЫЕ МОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ КРАНИОМЕТРИЧЕСКИХ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ ГОЛОВЫ И КРАНИАЛЬНОГО ИНДЕКСА У ДЕТЕЙ МЛАДШЕГО ШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье анализируются возрастные и половые особенности морфологических изменений краниометрических параметров головы и краниального указателя у детей младшего школьного возраста. Краниометрические показатели существенно различаются в зависимости от возраста и пола. Полученные результаты важны в таких областях, как хирургия, педиатрия, судебная медицина и ортодонтия. Развитие краниометрических исследований и их интеграция с новыми технологиями позволит нам и дальше расширять научные достижения в этой области.

Ключевые слова: краниометрические показатели, краниальный индекс, морфологические изменения.

Mavzuning dolzarbligi. Kraniometriya inson bosh suyagi o'Ichamlarini o'rganish bilan shug'ullanadigan ilmiy-tadqiqot yo'nalishlaridan biri bo'lib, anatomiya, antropologiya va tibbiyotda muhim ahamiyatga egadir. Kraniometrik ko'rsatkichlar yosh va jinsga qarab sezilarli o'zgarishlarga uchraydi, bu esa pediatriya, jarrohlik, sud-tibbiyot ekspertizasi va ortodontiyada katta ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ushbu maqolada kraniometrik o'Ichamlarning yoshga va jinsga xos morfologik o'zgarishlari hamda ularning klinik tibbiyotdagi dolzarbligi tahlil qilinadi.

Kraniometrik ko'rsatkichlarning yosh va jinsga xos o'zgarishlarini tibbiyotning turli sohalarida qo'llash mumkin. Pediatriya va bolalar jarrohligida tug'ma nuqsonlar (kraniosinostoz, mikrotsefaliya) va suyak rivojlanishi patologiyalarini aniqlashda yordam beradi. Ortopediya va ortodontiyada tish protezlari, ortodontik apparatlar tayyorlashda yuz va bosh suyaklarining o'Ichamlari hisobga olinadi. Sud-tibbiyot ekspertizasida kraniometrik o'Ichovlar orqali shaxsni identifikatsiya qilish va jinsini aniqlashda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Neyroxirurgiyada miya hajmi va bosh suyagi konfiguratsiyasi operatsion rejalashtirishda hisobga olinadi.

Tadqiqot maqsadi. Kichik maktab yoshidagi bolalarda boshning kraniometrik ko'rsatkichlari va kranial indeksning yoshga va jinsga xos morfologik o'zgarishlarini tahlil qilish.

Tadqiqot material va usullari. Tadqiqotning obyekti sifatida Andijon viloyati Izboskan tumani maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi bo'limiga qarashli 41-umumta'lim maktabida ta'lim olayotgan 1-6 sinfdagi (7-12 yosh) 180 nafar o'g'il va qiz bolalar olindi. Tadqiqotning uslublari: kraniometrik va variatsion-statistika usullari (A.M.Merkov va L.N.Polyakov bo'yicha).

Boshning gorizontaal aylanasini – bu glabella(g) bilan opistokranion (op) oralig'idagi aylana (sirkulyar) chiziq bo'lib, ushbu ko'rsatkich bolani tik turgan holatida santimetrli tasma bilan o'lchandi.

Boshning bo'ylama diametri - bu glabella (g) bilan opistokranion (op) orasidagi to'g'ri chiziq bo'lib, ushbu ko'rsatkich kallaning eng katta diametridir va bu ko'rsatkich tazomer bilan o'lchandi.

Boshning ko'ndalang diametri - bu ko'rsatkich chizig'i sagittal o'qqa nisbatan perpendikulyar holatda yo'nalib, miya qutisi yon devorlarining eng bo'rtib chiqqan nuqtalarini tutashtiradi. Bunda ikkala tomondagi eurion (eu) nuqtalari orasidagi masofa tazomer bilan o'lchandi.

$$\text{Kalla ko'rsatkichi} - \frac{\text{kallaning ko'ndalang diametri} \cdot 100}{\text{kallaning bo'ylama diametri}}$$

Guruhlardagi tekshiriluvchilarda boshning bo'ylama diametri uning ko'ndalang diametridan kattaroq o'lchamga ega, bu tananing uzunligiga bog'liq. Shu sababli uzun bo'yga ega kishilarning

kalla ko'rsatkichi past bo'yilarga qaraganda kichikroq bo'ladi. Ayollar va bolalarda nisbatan yuqori bosh ko'rsatkichi qayd etiladi, bu esa ulardagi nisbiy past bo'ylik bilan bog'liq bo'lishi mumkin. Organizmning o'sish jarayonida boshning bo'ylama diametri ko'ndalang diametriga qaraganda tezroq kattalashadi, buning oqibatida bosh ko'rsatkichi kichiklashib boradi. Kranial indeksni quyidagicha tahlil qilish mumkin: 74,9 gacha – dolixokraniya; 75,0-79,9 – mezokraniya; 80,0 va undan yuqori bo'lsa – braxikraniya.

Tadqiqot natijalari. Tadqiqotdan olingan natijalar shuni ko'rsatmoqdaki, boshning gorizontal aylanasi o'g'il bolalarda 7 yoshdan 12 yoshgacha kattalashishda davom etadi va $51,0 \pm 0,60$ smdan $P < 0,001$, $54,2 \pm 0,50$ smgacha $P < 0,001$ kattalashadi. 7-10 yoshdagi o'g'il bolalarda nisbatan intensiv o'sish kuzatilsa, 11-12 yoshlar orasida o'sishni sekinlashishini kuzatiladi. Qiz bolalarda ham boshning gorizontal aylanasi o'rganilgan yoshlar oralig'ida yoshga mos ravishda bir maromda o'sib borishi kuzatildi ($50,1 \pm 0,20$ smdan $P < 0,001$, $53,1 \pm 1,02$ smgacha $P < 0,001$). Nisbatan intensiv o'sish davri 7-10 yoshlar orasiga to'g'ri kelishi olib borilgan tadqiqot natijalarida o'z tasdig'ini topmoqda.

Boshning bo'ylama diametri 7 yoshdagi o'g'il bolalarda $16,0 \pm 0,02$ sm, $P < 0,001$ bo'lsa, 10 yoshda $16,4 \pm 0,20$ sm, $P < 0,001$, 12 yoshda esa $16,6 \pm 0,28$ smgacha $P < 0,001$, kattalashishi va bu davrda 4% ga ortishi kuzatiladi. Ko'rsatkichlarning eng jadal o'sish davri 7-10 yosh orasiga to'g'ri kelishi tadqiqot natijalaridan ma'lum bo'ldi. Qiz bolalarda esa kallaning bo'ylama diametri 7-12 yoshlar orasida $15,0 \pm 0,08$ smdan, $P < 0,001$, $16,3 \pm 0,20$ smgacha, $P < 0,001$ kattalashadi. Bu davrda ushbu ko'rsatkich 9 %ga oshadi. Qiz bolalarda kallaning bo'ylama diametri o'g'il bolalarga qaraganda o'rganilgan yoshlarda nisbatan ko'proq o'zgarishlarga yuz tutadi.

Diagramma №1

Kichik maktab yoshidagi bolalarda boshning gorizontal aylanasi ko'rsatkichlarining o'sish dinamikasi ($X \pm m$, sm da)

7-12 yoshdagi sub'ektlarda boshning bo'ylama diametri yoshga doir holda intensiv o'sib boradi. Tadqiqot olib borilgan hududdagi o'g'il bolalarda boshning bo'ylama diametrini eng tez o'sish davri 7-10 yoshda kuzatiladi. Ushbu hududda yashovchi qiz bolalarda esa boshning bo'ylama diametri o'g'il bolalarga qaraganda o'rganilgan yoshlarda nisbatan ko'proq o'zgarishlarga yuz tutadi.

7 yoshli o'g'il bolalarda boshning ko'ndalang diametri $14,1 \pm 0,20$ smni, $P < 0,01$, tashkil etsa, qiz bolalarda ushbu ko'rsatkich $14,0 \pm 0,22$ smga, $P < 0,01$, teng bo'ladi. Ushbu ko'rsatkich o'rganilgan yoshlarda o'g'il va qiz bolalarda o'sishda davom etadi va 12 yoshdagi o'g'il bolalarda $15,1 \pm 0,12$ sm, $P < 0,01$, shu yoshdagi qiz bolalarda $15,0 \pm 0,10$ smni, $P < 0,01$, tashkil etadi.

Boshning ko'ndalang diametri o'sishi 7-12 yosh orasidagi qiz bolalarda 7 %ga, shu yosh orasidagi o'g'il bolalarda esa 8 % ga oshadi. Ko'rsatkichlarning eng jadal o'sish davrlarihar ikkala jinsdagilarda ham 7-11 yoshlar orasiga to'g'ri keladi.

Diagramma №2

Kichik maktab yoshidagi bolalarda boshning bo'ylama diametri o'sish dinamikasi
($X \pm m$, sm da)

Diagramma №3

Kichik maktab yoshidagi bolalarda boshning ko'ndalang diametri o'sish dinamikasi
($X \pm m$, sm da)

Xulosa. Olib borilgan tadqiqot natijalarini ko'rsatishicha, qiz bolalarda asosiy kraniometrik ko'rsatkichlarning jadal o'sishi kichik maktab yoshi davrining 1-yarmiga ya'ni 8-10 yoshlar orasiga to'g'ri keladi, o'g'il bolalarda esa kalla suyagining o'sishi kichik maktab yoshi davrining 2-yarmida ya'ni 10-12 yoshlar orasida jadallashadi. Bu qiz bolalar kalla suyagining taraqqiyoti o'g'il bolalarnikidan erta boshlanishini ko'rsatadi.

Kichik maktab yoshidagi o'g'il bolalar va qiz bolalarning ayrim kraniometrik ko'rsatkichlarining o'sish dinamikasini ifodalovchi chiziqlarning kesishish holatini kuzatish mumkin. Bunday kesishuv nuqtalari ko'pincha 8-9 yoshlar orasida kuzatiladi. Kalla suyagining miya qismi kraniometrik ko'rsatkichlarida ikkala jinsdagi kichik maktab yoshidagi bolalarda muttasil o'sish jarayonini kuzatish mumkin. Kichik maktab yoshidagi bolalarning kalla suyagi braxikraniya tipida bo'ladi.

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